

Continuous Energy Subgroup Method

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ABSTRACT

The Continuous-Energy Subgroup Method (CESM) solves subgroup equations using a continuous-energy representation. The method rewrites the flat source MOC equation in reciprocal form, applies a linear-fractional transform, and expands energy-dependent quantities in a Cauchy-power basis, enabling linear coefficient-space updates with symbolic precomputation. CESM is demonstrated on a reflective 1D slab with U238 and H1 in an isolated-resonance window (220–250 eV). Across test cases, fuel-region effective U238 absorption cross sections agree with a fine-energy reference within 1.4%. The symbolic formulation allows the subgroup sweep to be performed once and reused to evaluate different resonance and source parameters, suggesting a path toward accurate, reusable within-group solutions for multigroup cross-section generation.

Keywords: Continuous energy subgroup, Multigroup cross-section generation

1. INTRODUCTION

Calculating multigroup cross-sections is a difficult process that must be performed with great care. Two main pathways exist in the deterministic transport world through the use of equivalence in dilution relying on precomputed homogeneous lookup tables with equivalences form with heterogeneous systems, or through using the subgroup method. The subgroup method solves the transport equation in a given group for different levels of cross-section values. It assumes that within this group the scattering source can be defined by the intermediate resonance model. [1, 2]

In practice, in each energy group, the cross-section of a resonant nuclide is divided by levels with associated weights. One can generate these cross-section levels directly from the data where the weights correspond to a projection on the energy band of the group, but these parameters will carry some dependence on dilution. Alternatively, the parameters are generated through an optimization process to match a subset of resonance integrals as a function of dilution or a selection of cross-section moments. Regardless of the approach, we end up with a parameter set $\{\sigma_n, w_n\}$ for each resonant nuclide in each energy group representing an absorption cross-section band and an associated weight.

Thus for each subgroup within the group of interest, a transport equation can be written with the scattering source:

$$\Omega \cdot \nabla \psi_n(\vec{r}, \Omega) + (N_0(\vec{r})\sigma_n + \Sigma_p(\vec{r}))\psi_n(\vec{r}, \Omega) = \frac{1}{4\pi}\lambda\Sigma_p(\vec{r}) + (1 - \lambda)\Sigma_p(\vec{r})\psi_n(\vec{r}, \Omega)$$

which we can re-arrange to

$$\Omega \cdot \nabla \psi_n(\vec{r}, \Omega) + (N_0(\vec{r})\sigma_n + \lambda\Sigma_p(\vec{r}))\psi_n(\vec{r}, \Omega) = \frac{1}{4\pi}\lambda\Sigma_p(\vec{r})$$

where ψ_n is the subgroup angular flux, N_0 is the nuclide density of the resonant nuclide, λ is the intermediate resonance parameter and Σ_p is the macroscopic potential scattering cross-section.

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The solution to this problem can be obtained using the same transport solver that will be used for the eigenvalue problem. Solutions are needed for each subgroup level of each group and for every resonant isotope. All spatial regions are solved simultaneously but one resonant nuclide at a time. One thing to note is that this equation is a pure absorbing problem and can thus be solved quite readily.

The goal of this paper is to evaluate the possibility of solving the subgroup equation only once, but in a symbolic form with a continuous energy representation where the solution would then be evaluated as needed across nuclides and resonance parameters. This idea stems from previous work providing an analytical solution to a continuous energy slowing down problem. [3] This paper describes a preliminary approach that gets us part of the way there. Section 2 describes the method which relies on a series expansion in a Cauchy basis set and recasting the method of characteristic equation in reciprocal space. Section 3 presents a series of test cases for groups with single resonances, with concluding remarks in Section 4.

2. METHODS

The starting point is the MOC equation with the flat source approximation. For a cell of thickness l with energy-dependent total cross section $\Sigma_t(E)$ and an E -independent volumetric source Q , the outgoing scalar flux satisfies

$$\Psi_{\text{out}}(E) = \Psi_{\text{in}}(E) e^{-\Sigma_t(E)l} + \frac{Q}{\Sigma_t(E)} (1 - e^{-\Sigma_t(E)l}). \quad (1)$$

In the subgroup method, the source Q is defined by the scattering cross-section making this a fixed source purely absorbing problem. However, instead of defining the absorption cross-section as a set of subgroups with associated weights representing the cross-section bands in an energy group, this work aims to maintain the continuous-energy representation and solve this equation symbolically. The idea is thus to solve this equation once for all groups over a given nuclide, but evaluate its output many times to calculate the within-groups spectrum averaged cross-sections for various cross-section and source parameters.

2.1. Reciprocal form and linearization

This equation is then solved by approximating the exponential by a truncated series. However, one of the major hurdles is finding a basis set that can represent both the cross-section and flux appropriately, especially in deep penetration problems near a resonance where the dip approaches 0 and the energy gap widens around the peak of the cross-section resonance as shown in Figure 1. This figure shows the angular flux attenuation through a slab using a brute-force approach and illustrates the difficulty in representing the flux shape from a basis set that can also well represent the cross-section.

Many attempts were made that led to negative flux values and instabilities. One approach that has proven promising is solving the reciprocal form of the within-cell MOC equation:

$$\frac{1}{\psi_{\text{out}}(E)} = \frac{1}{\psi_{\text{in}}(E) e^{-\Sigma_t(E)l} + \frac{Q}{\Sigma_t(E)} (1 - e^{-\Sigma_t(E)l})}. \quad (2)$$

Let's define the reciprocal flux as $e(E) = 1/\Psi(E)$ and introduce the following notational simplifications:

$$t(E) = e^{l\Sigma_t(E)}, \quad \beta(E) = \frac{\Sigma_t(E)}{Q} \frac{1}{(1 - e^{-l\Sigma_t(E)})}, \quad (3)$$

so that the reciprocal form can be written as

$$e_{\text{out}}(E) = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{t} \psi_{\text{in}} + \frac{1}{\beta}} = \frac{t(E) \beta(E)}{t(E) + \beta(E) \psi_{\text{in}}(E)} = \frac{t(E) \beta(E) e_{\text{in}}(E)}{t(E) e_{\text{in}}(E) + \beta(E)}. \quad (4)$$

Figure 1. Attenuation of the angular flux through a material with a resonant nuclide.

The cell solution for e_{out} is a scalar Möbius transform (linear fractional transformation), which facilitates a linear coefficient-space update using homogeneous coordinates. The reciprocal flux can thus be represented by the homogeneous coordinates (u, v) such that $e = u/v$ (and $\psi = v/u$). Substituting $e = u/v$ into (4) yields the linear update

$$u_{out} = (t\beta) \cdot u_{in}, \quad v_{out} = t \cdot u_{in} + \beta \cdot v_{in}, \quad (5)$$

where “ \cdot ” denotes the energy-dependent multiplication operator acting on the coefficient representation introduced next. Additionally, a common scaling $(u, v) \mapsto (u/s, v/s)$ leaves $e = u/v$ invariant, thus a projective rescale is performed after each cell so that $v_0 = 1$.

2.2. Series expansion

All energy-dependent fields are expanded using a Cauchy-power basis represented by function $z(E)$ representing a single resonance of the resonant nuclide, so that

$$F(E) \approx F(z) = \sum_{k=0}^K F_k z^k, \quad z^m z^n = z^{m+n}. \quad (6)$$

Because the basis is multiplicatively closed, multiplication by any expanded function is a Cauchy product in coefficient space:

$$(F \cdot X)_k = \sum_{m=0}^k F_m X_{k-m}, \quad k = 0, \dots, K, \quad (7)$$

i.e., a truncated convolution. We write this action as $X \mapsto F \circ X$.

The material cross section is expanded as

$$\Sigma_t(z) = \sum_{k=0}^K s_k z^k, \quad (8)$$

where only s_0 and s_1 are non-zero and represent the potential scattering and absorption cross-sections of the material. The coefficient vectors $T = \{T_k\}$ and $B = \{B_k\}$ corresponding to t and β are obtained by truncated series:

$$t(z) = \exp(l \Sigma_t(z)) = \exp(l s_0) \exp(l [\Sigma_t(z) - s_0]) = \sum_{k=0}^K T_k z^k, \quad (9)$$

$$\beta(z) = \frac{\Sigma_t(z)}{Q} \frac{1}{1 - \exp(-l \Sigma_t(z))} = \sum_{k=0}^K B_k z^k. \quad (10)$$

For numerical stability, we factor out the constant part s_0 in (9) and expand only the zero-constant remainder before truncation; similarly, when forming (10) we factor $1 - \exp(-l s_0)$. The T and B are precomputed symbolically and then evaluated per cell.

2.3. Coefficient-space cell update

With the coefficient vectors $u, v \in \mathbb{R}^K$ representing the incoming reciprocal state $e = u/v$, the outgoing state for a cell with operators T, B is

$$u_{\text{out}} = (T \circ B) \circ u_{\text{in}}, \quad (11)$$

$$v_{\text{out}} = T \circ u_{\text{in}} + B \circ v_{\text{in}}, \quad (12)$$

where each “ \circ ” is the truncated convolution (7). Since T and B do not commute exactly at finite K , we use the symmetric composition for $T \circ B$,

$$(T \circ B) \circ u \approx \frac{1}{2} \left(T \circ (B \circ u) + B \circ (T \circ u) \right), \quad (13)$$

which reduces non-commutation (truncation) error with negligible cost. After each cell we apply a projective rescale

$$s = \text{sign}(v_0) \max(|v_0|, \varepsilon), \quad (u, v) \leftarrow (u/s, v/s), \quad (14)$$

with a small ε to prevent division by zero. This keeps the homogeneous pair well scaled while preserving $e = u/v$.

Constant- Σ_t special case. If a cell contains a total cross-section only defined by the s_0 term (i.e. constant in energy) so that $T = [t_0, 0, \dots]$ and $B = [b_0, 0, \dots]$, the update reduces exactly to the scalar map

$$u_{\text{out}} = (t_0 b_0) u_{\text{in}}, \quad v_{\text{out}} = t_0 u_{\text{in}} + b_0 v_{\text{in}}, \quad (15)$$

which cannot generate spurious higher modes.

2.4. Sweeping and interfaces

Sweeping can be done across varying materials as long as all information is defined using the same basis $z(E)$; only the evaluation of the coefficient operators (T, B) change with the local (l, Σ_t, Q) . A

conventional MOC sweep is then performed from boundary to boundary until convergence of the reciprocal flux. In a purely absorbing problem with a known source, convergence is achieved quickly as only the initial boundary condition needs to be iterated on. At the interface of two cells, the *post-cell* pairs become the incoming reciprocal pair (u_{in}, v_{in}) .

For simplicity, the cell-averaged reciprocal angular flux is evaluated as the average of incoming and outgoing terms instead of the more traditional analytical calculation of average angular flux of a particular segment. The average angular flux can be calculated directly as v/u , thus the cell quantities can be averaged and accumulated in the flux space.

Knowing (u_{out}, v_{out}) and (u_{in}, v_{in}) be the interface pairs of a given cell, obtained from a single sweep across a segment, the arithmetic mean of the angular flux inside the cell is approximated by,

$$\bar{\psi} = \frac{v_{avg}}{u_{avg}}$$

which is represented by

$$u_{avg} = u_{in} \circ u_{out}, \quad v_{avg} = \frac{1}{2} (v_{in} \circ u_{out}) + \frac{1}{2} (v_{out} \circ u_{in}). \quad (16)$$

Similarly, the scalar flux can be computed by the sum of the average angular fluxes. In the simplified case with two angles of equal weights, the *sum* of the two flux contributions yields the scalar flux

$$\phi_{cell} = \bar{\psi}_1 + \bar{\psi}_2 = \frac{v_{sum}}{u_{sum}}$$

represented by

$$u_{sum} = u_1 \circ u_2, \quad v_{sum} = (v_1 \circ u_2) + (v_2 \circ u_1). \quad (17)$$

This can be extended to more angles, each with unique weights, following a similar process.

2.5. Energy condensed cross-section

The scalar flux in each cell is thus represented by the pair (u_{sum}, v_{sum}) , which are coefficients in the Cauchy-basis set with a basis set still defined symbolically. The MOC sweep and iterations are performed until the coefficients are converged without having defined the actual value of the cross-section. If we define the cross-section such that $s_0 = \sum_{i=0}^I N_i \sigma_{p,i}$ and $s_1 = N_0$ for the resonant nuclide ($i = 0$) and $s_1 = 0$ for all other materials as commonly done in self-shielding calculation, the solution remains valid within a group regardless of the magnitude and width of a resonance. The solution also remains valid across groups.

3. RESULTS

To demonstrate this new approach, a set of simple 1D slowing down problems using the subgroup form with the narrow resonance source approximation will be used. The reference solution will be computed through a brute-force approach where the energy variable will be divided very finely. This is akin to the direct subgroup approach with fine energy resolution. The analysis will only account for two polar angles as the focus of this paper is on the energy variable. The mesh spacing was selected to be 0.05 cm which was shown to be smaller than needed for spatial convergence and was kept constant to facilitate comparison. The coefficients representing the T and B operators were computed using the python symbolic solver SymPy up to 35th order. These coefficients are functions of the cross-section parameters for each cell s_0 and s_1 , and the segment length l .

The analysis will focus on a reflective slab problem with a central region of 1.4 cm composed of U238 surrounded by H1 slabs of 0.3 cm. The nuclide density of U238 is set at 0.023 atoms/barns.cm² with a

potential scattering cross-section of 10 barns and the nuclide density of H1 will be varied as an input parameter (potential scattering cross-section of 20 barns). These values were selected for simplicity but are also somewhat representative of a PWR pin cell with dimensions representing an effective length such that the polar angle can be set to 1 thus simplifying the implementation, and concentrations and potential scattering cross-section values that also account for other nuclides typically found in PWRs.

The Cauchy basis set was selected for providing a good representation of nuclear cross-sections. For illustration of the method, the 220-250eV range of U238 was selected as it includes an isolated s-wave resonance (located at 237.3985 eV and modeled with a peak of 215 barns and a $\Gamma = 0.3$ as illustrated in Figure 1). The peak value will be varied to demonstrate the accuracy of the method and its potential in representing a physical case. Convergence issues were encountered for under-moderated cases with a large resonance where the process would not converge or lead to unrealistic flux solutions. This is mainly caused by the choice of the basis-set and the iterative process that applies convolution integrals repeatedly which grows the high order coefficients. This can be addressed by increasing the expansion order. Alternatively, the high order tail was rebalanced at the fuel-moderator boundary. The rebalancing consists of mapping the high order coefficients back to a lower order basis and enforcing a constraint such as a flux value between the two expansions. This has proven quite effective at stabilizing the convergence process, but leads to a user-selected input on how to rebalance. Future work, will look at better models for rebalancing the high order modes in order to preserve the quantities of interest.

The test cases span a range of cross-section peaks from 100 barns to 500 barns and a range of H1 density from 0.05 atoms/barns.cm² (similar to a PWR) to 0.5 atoms/barns.cm². The effective cross-sections are computed using:

$$\sigma_a = \frac{\int \sigma(E)\phi(E)dE}{\int \phi(E)dE}. \quad (18)$$

For CESM, the (u, v) parameters representing the scalar flux were first converged over the problem. Once the symbolic solution is established, and the resonance parameters defined, a scalar flux over 1000 bins in the 220eV - 250eV range is constructed and used to evaluate the effective absorption cross-section. It should be noted that the converged symbolic solution is performed once and only the flux reconstruction is performed for each individual case. The reference solution uses a brute force approach using the same 1000 bins structure. Tables I to III provide the average effective cross-section in the fuel region for varying resonance peaks and H1 density. In highly moderated cases, CESM agrees very well with the reference solution, however the accuracy degrades as moderation is reduced.

Table I. Effective U238 absorption cross-section (100 barns peak and $\Gamma = 0.3$) as a function of H1 density

H1 density (atoms/barns.cm)	0.5	0.1	0.05
Reference (barns)	1.90	1.68	1.48
CESM (barns)	1.90	1.68	1.48
Relative Error (%)	0.00	-0.27	0.00

Table II. Effective U238 absorption cross-section (215 barns peak and $\Gamma = 0.3$) as a function of H1 density

H1 density (atoms/barns.cm)	0.5	0.1	0.05
Reference (barns)	3.06	2.67	2.33
CESM (barns)	3.06	2.65	2.31
Relative Error (%)	0.00	-0.94	-0.65

Table III. Effective U238 absorption cross-section (500 barns peak and $\Gamma = 0.3$) as a function of H1 density

H1 density (atoms/barns.cm)	0.5	0.1	0.05
Reference (barns)	4.94	4.31	3.75
CESM (barns)	4.94	4.26	3.71
Relative Error (%)	0.00	-1.34	-1.01

Focusing on the case with a peak cross-section of 215 barns, Figure 2 shows the scalar flux for different spatial positions in the problem. The figure only shows selected positions in the left half of the problem for clarity. The values at 0.075 cm and 0.275 cm are in the moderator region with the rest being in the fuel region. The main difference between the two cases that helps explain the results in the previous tables is the large flux depression that is still present in the water, away from the resonant nuclide.

Figure 3 shows the spatially dependent effective absorption cross-section in the fuel for the same two cases. Once again, the agreement of the highly moderated case can be seen where the effective cross-section profile is captured with great accuracy. However, the lower moderation case shows great spatial fidelity with a clear constant bias indicating a misrepresentation of the source.

Figure 2. Scalar flux for the 215 barns case

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a first attempt at solving the subgroup equations with a continuous energy representation of the cross-section. The method relies on the reciprocal form of the MOC equation and a linear fractional transformation. The cross-section is represented as a Cauchy distribution and all other terms are expanded as a power series of the same basis set. The method was tested on a simple slab problem alternating fuel and moderator, and demonstrated accuracy on the order of 1% for calculating the effective absorption cross-section. Future work will focus on evaluating the effective cross-section in a wider group with many resonances, as well as analyzing different rebalancing options.

Figure 3. Spatial dependence of the U238 effective cross-section for the 215 barns case

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